

MUHANDISLIK

& IQTISODIYOT

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ИМЕНИ Г.В. ПЛЕХАНОВА
ТАШКЕНТСКИЙ ФИЛИАЛ

muhandislik **& iqtisodiyot**

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05.01.01 – Muhandislik geometriyasi va kompyuter grafikasi. Audio va video texnologiyalari
05.01.02 – Tizimli tahlil, boshqaruv va axborotni qayta ishlash
05.01.03 – Informatikaning nazariy asoslari
05.01.04 – Hisoblash mashinalari, majmualari va kompyuter tarmoqlarining matematik va dasturiy ta'minoti
05.01.05 – Axborotlarni himoyalash usullari va tizimlari. Axborot xavfsizligi
05.01.06 – Hisoblash texnikasi va boshqaruv tizimlarining elementlari va qurilmalari
05.01.07 – Matematik modellashtirish
05.01.11 – Raqamli texnologiyalar va sun'iy intellekt
05.02.00 – Mashinasozlik va mashinashunoslik
05.02.08 – Yer usti majmualari va uchish apparatlari
05.03.02 – Metrologiya va metrologiya ta'minoti
05.04.01 – Telekommunikatsiya va kompyuter tizimlari, telekommunikatsiya tarmoqlari va qurilmalari. Axborotlarni taqsimlash
05.05.03 – Yorug'lik texnikasi. Maxsus yoritish texnologiyasi
05.05.05 – Issiqlik texnikasining nazariy asoslari
05.05.06 – Qayta tiklanadigan energiya turlari asosidagi energiya qurilmalari
05.06.01 – To'qimachilik va yengil sanoat ishlab chiqarishlari materialshunosligi
05.08.03 – Temir yo'l transportini ishlatish
05.08.06 – "G'ildirakli va gusenisali mashinalar va ularni ishlatish" (texnika fanlari)
05.09.01 – Qurilish konstruksiyalari, bino va inshootlar
05.09.04 – Suv ta'minoti. Kanalizatsiya. Suv havzalarini muhofazalovchi qurilish tizimlari
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08.00.04 – Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
08.00.05 – Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
08.00.06 – Ekonometrika va statistika
08.00.07 – Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
08.00.08 – Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
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08.00.16 – Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
08.00.17 – Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

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FEMALE ENTREPRENEURSHIP AND GREEN INITIATIVES: A CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. This study offers a conceptual framework for sustainable development in Uzbekistan and investigates the relationship between green initiatives and female entrepreneurship. The study applies a conceptual approach by synthesizing theoretical and empirical research on sustainable development, green entrepreneurship, and women's entrepreneurship. The findings indicate that government support, human capital, social capital, and access to finance are important enabling factors that encourage female entrepreneurs to implement eco-friendly business practices. Green initiatives, including waste reduction, efficient resource use, and energy-saving technologies, enhance business competitiveness, reduce operating costs, and promote long-term growth. The proposed framework provides a useful basis for both academic research and policy development in the context of Uzbekistan, where significant government initiatives are being implemented to support women's entrepreneurship and green transformation.

Keywords: female entrepreneurship, green initiatives, sustainable development, conceptual framework, Uzbekistan.

Annotatsiya. Mazkur tadqiqot O'zbekistonda barqaror rivojlanishning konseptual asoslarini yoritadi hamda "yashil" tashabbuslar va ayollar tadbirkorligi o'rtasidagi bog'liqlikni tahlil qiladi. Tadqiqotda barqaror rivojlanish, yashil tadbirkorlik va ayollar tadbirkorligiga oid nazariy hamda empirik tadqiqotlarni sintez qilish asosida konseptual yondashuv qo'llanilgan. Tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko'rsatadiki, davlat tomonidan qo'llab-quvvatlash, inson kapitali, ijtimoiy kapital va moliyaviy resurslardan foydalanish imkoniyati ayol tadbirkorlarni ekologik jihatdan barqaror biznes amaliyotlarini joriy etishga undovchi muhim omillar hisoblanadi. Chiqindilarni kamaytirish, resurslardan samarali foydalanish va energiya tejovchi texnologiyalar kabi "yashil" tashabbuslar biznes raqobatbardoshligini oshiradi, operatsion xarajatlarni kamaytiradi hamda uzoq muddatli o'sishni ta'minlaydi. Taklif etilgan konseptual model O'zbekistonda ayollar tadbirkorligini va yashil transformatsiyani qo'llab-quvvatlash bo'yicha amalga oshirilayotgan davlat tashabbuslari sharoitida ilmiy tadqiqotlar hamda siyosiy qarorlar ishlab chiqish uchun foydali asos bo'lib xizmat qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: ayollar tadbirkorligi, yashil tashabbuslar, barqaror rivojlanish, konseptual model, O'zbekiston.

Аннотация. В данном исследовании предлагается концептуальная основа устойчивого развития в Узбекистане и анализируется взаимосвязь между «зелёными» инициативами и женским предпринимательством. В работе используется концептуальный подход, основанный на синтезе теоретических и эмпирических исследований в области устойчивого развития, зелёного предпринимательства и женского предпринимательства. Результаты исследования показывают, что государственная поддержка, человеческий капитал, социальный капитал и доступ к финансовым ресурсам являются важными факторами, стимулирующими женщин-предпринимателей к внедрению экологически устойчивых бизнес-практик. «Зелёные» инициативы, включая сокращение отходов, эффективное использование ресурсов и энергосберегающие технологии, повышают конкурентоспособность бизнеса, снижают операционные расходы и способствуют долгосрочному росту. Предложенная концептуальная модель служит полезной основой как для научных исследований, так и для разработки государственной политики в условиях Узбекистана, где реализуются масштабные инициативы по поддержке женского предпринимательства и зелёной трансформации.

Ключевые слова: женское предпринимательство, зелёные инициативы, устойчивое развитие, концептуальная модель, Узбекистан.

INTRODUCTION

Green business practices create broad opportunities for reducing waste and pollution, lowering operating

costs, supporting sustainable local economic development, and strengthening entrepreneurs' competitive advantages. Proactive green practices can enhance a company's benefits while reducing its environmental impact [1].

Through a number of presidential decrees and national initiatives, the Government of Uzbekistan has established a comprehensive legislative framework to support female entrepreneurship. The Strategy for Achieving Gender Equality in the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030, approved by the Senate of the Oliy Majlis through Resolution No. SQ-297-IV, provides a comprehensive approach to implementing the principle of equality between women and men in all areas of decision-making [2]. Building on this foundation, the Presidential Decree "National Program for Enhancing Women's Participation in All Spheres of Economic, Political, and Social Life (2022–2026)" was adopted to provide systematic support for women and families across all sectors of the national economy [3].

In addition, Presidential Decree No. PD-50 of March 19, 2025, "On Measures to Enhance the Role of Small and Medium-Sized Businesses in the Economy," allocated 2.5 trillion soums at preferential interest rates for women's entrepreneurship. The decree also aims to launch at least 200 startups in areas such as energy conservation and green technologies [4]. Although these legislative initiatives demonstrate Uzbekistan's strong commitment to promoting female entrepreneurship, an important issue still requires empirical investigation: the gap between policy objectives and actual business outcomes among women entrepreneurs.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Globally, female entrepreneurship has become an important driver of sustainable development and economic growth. According to the core ideas proposed by Brush (2002), women approach entrepreneurship differently from men by combining business activities with family, personal life, and community responsibilities [5].

This perspective continues to influence contemporary research. Welter [6] expanded this understanding through a contextual approach, emphasizing that entrepreneurship should be evaluated within its specific social, institutional, and environmental context rather than in isolation.

Several studies have examined how green entrepreneurship contributes to women's empowerment in developing countries, with particular attention to Saudi Arabia. One study investigated the effects of green entrepreneurial skills (GESS), green opportunities (GOS), and green incentives (GIS) on women's empowerment (WEN) and green entrepreneurship performance (GEP) using survey data from 314 women entrepreneurs and structural equation modeling. The findings showed that GOS positively influenced both empowerment and entrepreneurship performance, while GESS demonstrated a more complex relationship with these variables. GIS also produced mixed effects, positively influencing entrepreneurship while demonstrating varying effects on empowerment. Importantly, green entrepreneurship performance acted as a mediating factor between incentives and women's empowerment. Based on these findings, the authors proposed an integrated framework linking skills, opportunities, incentives, entrepreneurship, and empowerment in order to support policymakers in designing inclusive strategies and reducing gender-related barriers within the green economy [7].

In a more recent study, Iqbal et al. [8] conducted a comprehensive bibliometric analysis showing that research on female entrepreneurship has evolved significantly — from viewing women mainly as necessity-driven entrepreneurs to recognizing them as innovators and agents of social change. Despite this progress, substantial structural and cultural barriers still persist globally, including limited access to business networks, skill gaps, and social norms that place a disproportionate share of caregiving responsibilities on women.

In a contemporary empirical study, Ibodullayeva [9] applied logistic regression modeling and found that digital literacy and government support positively influence women's entrepreneurial success in Uzbekistan, whereas socio-cultural barriers continue to create certain limitations for women in business activities.

Potluri [10] summarized the foundational concepts of ecofeminism, green entrepreneurship, and women's entrepreneurship, presenting a new business paradigm that addresses important research gaps at the macro-, meso-, and micro-levels.

The normative foundation of this research is further supported by the concept of sustainable development introduced by World Commission on Environment and Development [11], which defines sustainable development as meeting present needs without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. Building on this concept, systematic literature reviews covering the period from 2004 to 2024 have analyzed the landscape of green entrepreneurship, identifying its major drivers and outcomes and positioning it as an important force in promoting sustainable business models amid growing environmental challenges.

Gunawan et al. [12] conducted a systematic literature review aimed at developing a gender-based

theoretical framework explaining differences in ecopreneurship drivers and practices among female and male entrepreneurs. Their study reviewed gender-inclusive factors across the fields of female entrepreneurship, ecopreneurship, and ecological innovation. The findings highlighted that empirical evidence regarding gender-specific drivers of ecopreneurial behavior remains limited and fragmented. Through qualitative analysis, the authors further demonstrated that entrepreneurs are motivated to adopt ecopreneurship practices by values such as self-enhancement, conservation, and transcendence. However, intersections of identity — including gender, religion, and ethnicity — significantly influence these motivations, particularly in collectivist Asian cultures where community-oriented values often prevail over individualistic ones.

In another empirical investigation conducted within a developing economy, Aldoghan [13] examined the impact of green entrepreneurial skills, opportunities, and incentives on women's empowerment and green entrepreneurship performance. The results indicated that these factors generally exerted a positive influence on both women's empowerment and entrepreneurial performance.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Based on a thorough analysis and synthesis of theoretical and empirical studies on female entrepreneurship, green initiatives, and sustainable development, this study applies a conceptual research approach. Unlike empirical studies that rely on primary data collection, conceptual research aims to synthesize existing knowledge and develop a theoretical framework that clarifies the relationships between key concepts. According to Jabareen [14], a conceptual framework is a network of interrelated concepts that collectively provides a comprehensive understanding of a particular phenomenon.

The study examines institutional records and policy documents related to women's entrepreneurship in Uzbekistan, as well as previous studies conducted in other countries. Particular attention is given to research on women's empowerment, environmental sustainability, and green entrepreneurship. A critical analysis of the selected literature is conducted to identify the key factors, barriers, and opportunities associated with the adoption of green initiatives by female entrepreneurs.

Based on this synthesis, the study proposes a conceptual framework explaining how green initiatives can support the long-term development of female entrepreneurship in Uzbekistan. The framework emphasizes the importance of human capital, social capital, government support, and access to finance in promoting environmentally responsible business practices.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

According to the literature review, green initiatives provide female entrepreneurs in Uzbekistan with a promising strategic development pathway. Research from several countries consistently shows that by incorporating eco-friendly practices into their business models, female entrepreneurs can achieve both social and economic benefits. These practices include waste reduction, efficient resource use, the adoption of eco-friendly materials, and the application of energy-saving technologies.

The reviewed studies indicate that the adoption of green initiatives by female entrepreneurs is influenced by several interconnected factors. Human capital, which includes education, entrepreneurial skills, and environmental awareness, enables women entrepreneurs to identify and use sustainable business opportunities more effectively. Social capital, including professional networks, mentorship, and family support, facilitates access to knowledge, information, and opportunities for collaboration. Access to finance is also essential, as the introduction of green technologies often requires initial investment. In addition, government support in the form of subsidies, training programs, and preferential lending plays an important role in promoting environmentally responsible business practices.

Based on these findings, this study proposes a conceptual framework in which government support, access to finance, social capital, and human capital serve as enabling factors that encourage the adoption of green initiatives. In turn, green initiatives contribute to the sustainable development of female entrepreneurship by increasing business competitiveness, reducing operating costs, improving market reputation, and creating long-term growth opportunities.

By integrating female entrepreneurship and green initiatives into a unified analytical framework, the conceptual model developed in this study expands existing research. It also emphasizes practical ways in which sustainability-oriented practices can support the long-term growth of women-owned businesses and adapts global findings to the context of Uzbekistan.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Green initiatives and female entrepreneurship are becoming increasingly important drivers of sustainable economic growth. The analysis of theoretical and empirical studies demonstrates that by adopting environmentally responsible business practices, female entrepreneurs can enhance business competitiveness, reduce operating costs, and create long-term value.

The proposed conceptual framework indicates that government support, human capital, social capital, and access to finance are key enabling factors that encourage the adoption of green initiatives. By promoting business expansion, innovation, and resilience, these initiatives contribute to the long-term development of female entrepreneurship.

The integration of sustainability-oriented practices offers significant opportunities in the context of Uzbekistan, where major legislative and institutional efforts are being implemented to support both women's entrepreneurship and green transformation. The findings of this study provide both a theoretical foundation and practical recommendations for policymakers, financial institutions, and business support organizations seeking to strengthen the role of female entrepreneurs in building a more inclusive and sustainable economy.

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